

Diseased TN1 plants consistently gave higher percentages of infective insects, longer retention periods, and greater percentages of infected seedlings than diseased plants of IR8 and IR34 as virus sources, regardless of acquisition access time (see table).

When 1,800 *N. virescens* adults acquired the virus from IR8, IR34, and TN1, then inoculated IR8, IR34, and TN1 as recipient hosts, the insects' infectivity was not identical (see figure). Differences also occurred in retention period and percentage of infected seedlings. ■

Seasonal incidence of tungro on selected varieties

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Seven prerelease and three standard varieties (see table) were evaluated for tungro incidence in Aduthurai during kuruvai, samba, and thaladi seasons. Plantings were made on the 10th, 20th, and 30th of each month from June to November 1978 and percentages of infected plants were noted after 9 weeks.

Tungro occurred in plantings from July through November 1978.

IR34 was less affected than the other varieties. ■

Percentage of infective *Nephotettix virescens* vectors produced on 3 recipient hosts by 3 tungro source varieties. IRRI.

Rice tungro virus incidence on various cultivars. Aduthurai. India.

Planting date	Rice tungro virus incidence (%)										Mean
	ADT31	AD7486	AS3704	AD6120	AD6970	AD7211	AD5231	AD13893	IR34	IR20	
10 Jun	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20 "	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
30 "	2.6	-	-	-	-	5.7	-	2.5	1.7	-	1.3
10 Jul	5.2	-	2.6	1.6	3.9	15.2	-	8.2	6.7	1.5	4.5
20 "	6.4	2.6	5.9	5.2	6.6	19.9	1.2	13.2	14.1	4.3	7.7
30 "	9.7	4.4	8.5	7.7	12.1	15.4	4.1	17.4	8.0	5.8	9.3
10 Aug	13.8	12.3	3.9	6.6	8.9	6.2	16.8	8.6	6.5	14.8	9.8
20 "	18.5	5.3	14.8	16.1	9.2	7.2	12.4	19.6	6.8	6.0	11.6
30 "	34.9	4.1	13.1	17.4	29.0	4.7	2.7	58.9	5.0	5.4	29.1
10 Sep	64.6	4.9	19.2	17.3	88.3	69.6	39.1	92.4	14.2	6.0	41.6
20 "	92.4	27.5	72.9	63.5	61.3	86.6	81.9	92.0	19.2	86.1	68.3
30 "	98.6	99.8	83.9	97.4	81.9	93.3	28.4	94.7	30.6	90.9	80.0
10 Oct	100.0	84.9	94.3	61.8	100.0	68.4	42.0	84.8	45.6	53.0	73.5
20 "	95.6	56.7	91.9	78.8	93.7	24.4	43.1	52.4	36.8	20.5	59.4
30 "	100.0	64.9	100.0	68.0	100.0	65.5	83.3	82.9	36.1	50.9	75.2
10 Nov	91.5	26.2	89.0	67.0	76.6	28.9	57.4	23.4	24.2	13.3	50.0
20 "	84.5	20.5	85.3	78.8	65.6	17.5	19.1	84.6	22.1	12.4	49.0
30 "	85.4	16.0	82.7	25.3	71.7	14.3	17.7	44.3	19.0	17.9	39.4
Mean	50.2	23.9	42.6	34.0	44.9	30.1	24.4	43.3	16.4	21.6	